

Policy Brief #1

Evaluating Social-Ecological Inequalities for a Just Transition in Brussels-Capital Region

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1. Evaluating Social-Ecological Inequalities for a Just Transition in the Brussels Capital Region

Over the past few years, the concept of “just transition” has become increasingly present in the political realm at all levels of governance (Stavis and Felli, 2020; Bauler et al., 2019). It can notably be found in the Paris Agreement and subsequent COP26 Just Transition Declaration adopted by the United Nations. And, under the mantra “leaving no one behind”, the European Green Deal has begun to operationalize just transition imperatives through the ‘Social Climate Fund’ and the ‘Just Transition Mechanism’. The just transition has also recently been the subject of a wide-ranging societal dialogue in Belgium, as part of the [Etats Généraux de la Transition Juste](#).

At the level of the Brussels Capital Region (BCR), the regional government has made the just transition a guiding principle of its climate policy and integrated it in 2021 in the [Brussels Code on Air, Climate and Energy Management](#) (COBRACE). This legal text, which forms the basis of the principal environmental strategies and plans of the BCR, states that the regional climate policy should be guided by “the principle of social justice and just transition, which implies that the prevention and reduction of social inequalities and situations of precariousness are an integral part of the development and implementation of climate policies”. To operationalise this principle, the Brussels government has, in its [Air Climate Energy Plan](#) adopted in April 2023, made the following two main commitments:

1. “To **collect and publish indicators on the state of environmental and social inequalities** in the Brussels-Capital Region, a project led by IBSA with the participation of Bruxelles Environnement, Perspective.Brussels and the Observatoire de la Santé et du Social;
2. Integrate into sectoral public policies a **reflection on the identification of levers for reducing environmental and social inequalities**” (Bruxelles Environnement 2023, p. 168).

While this is certainly a good start, which reflects a comprehensive conception of just transition as social-ecological project aimed at addressing, in an integrated way, social and ecological challenges¹, there is still a need to broaden this definition to integrate *ecological* inequalities, or those related to the non-human domain of the living world. At the same time, it is essential to expand definitions of “environmental and social inequalities” to consider inequalities beyond simply access to environmental goods and exposure to environmental harms. Namely, inequalities in participation and recognition of distinct experiences and needs should be assessed and reduced.

The [COGITO project](#) adopts a broad conception of ‘just transition’, which is understood as a social-ecological transition guided by both social-environmental and ecological justice imperatives. In other words, this conception of just transition rests on **social-ecological justice principles** (see [Figure 1](#)) (Fransolet et Vanhille, 2023). Bridging social-environmental and ecological justice, the social-ecological justice framework “emphasizes the interlinkages and interactions between social and ecological developments” (Grossmann et al., 2022, pg. 1411). Until now, (social-)environmental justice has typically excluded the needs of non-humans, while ecological justice considerations have not been thoroughly integrated with the needs of humans (Schlosberg, 2007; Pope et al., 2021). However, striving for social-environmental and ecological justice imperatives can help to ensure that all humans are protected from environmental harms, while nature is protected from negative human interventions (Yaka, 2019; Gunnarsson-Östling and Svenfelt, 2018). Given the inextricable connection between human and non-human well-being, as well as the unique and intensified social-ecological challenges that cities face, there is a need to consider both human and non-human needs in urban planning for the just transition.

¹ This contrasts with the narrow conception of just transition implemented in the EU Green Deal, which operationalizes it mainly as a correction of the potential negative social impacts of climate change mitigation policies (Sabato and Vanhille, 2024; Laurent, 2023b; Fransolet and Vanhille, 2023)

Figure 1. Social-ecological justice (adapted from Fransolet and Laurent, forthcoming)

In this policy brief we propose an evaluation tool to support the implementation of the commitments of the BCR to 1) collect and publish indicators on the state of environmental and social inequalities and 2) to reflect on the identification of levers for reducing environmental and social inequalities. This **tool enables evaluation of social-ecological inequalities** in a particular context and could thus be used by the region to support its commitments to a just transition. This evaluation tool draws its inspiration and further expands upon a tool developed by Fransolet and Laurent (forthcoming).

Below, we present the social-ecological inequalities framework and explain its main elements (Section 2). Then, we **illustrate its application for diagnosing social-ecological inequalities in mobility in the Brussels Capital Region** (Section 3).

2. The Social-Ecological Inequalities Framework

We put forward a framework that considers five types of social-ecological inequalities (see Figure 2), expanding upon the tri-dimensional justice framework that is typically considered in the literature (i.e.: comprising distributive, procedural and recognitional justice) (see for e.g., Schlosberg, 2007). Not only does this framework includes the unequal **distribution** of environmental goods and burdens, unequal **participation** in planning processes, and unequal **recognition** of the needs of vulnerable/vulnerabilized groups, but also unequal **contribution** to environmental degradation and unequal **impacts** of environmental policies (Laurent, 2023a).

Figure 2. Framework of social-ecological inequalities

We posit that these five types of social-ecological inequalities can be observed across different spatial and temporal scales, between 1) individuals and social groups within the same generation (**intra-generational** justice), 2) individuals and social groups of different generations (**inter-generational** justice), 3) humans and non-humans (**inter-species** justice), and 4) individuals living within and beyond a given territory, from a global perspective (**cosmopolitan** justice). We thus broaden the ‘3 Is of justice’ approach developed by Gupta et al. (2022) as part of the ‘safe and just Earth system boundaries’ framework (Rockström et al., 2023) by integrating cosmopolitan justice. This last form of justice, which has a long history in global justice literature, is becoming increasingly popular in the just transition literature, as it reflects the international environmental commitments of states, such as those set out in the Paris Agreement (Hazrati et Heffron, 2021).

In the table below (Table 1), we present a set of *guiding questions* to assess the five types of social-ecological inequalities experienced when considering respectively intragenerational, intergenerational, interspecies, and cosmopolitan justice. These questions can be applied to an entire territory (e.g., municipality, region, country...) or to a particular domain (e.g., mobility, housing, food...) within a territory.

Table 1 Guiding questions to assess the five types of social-ecological inequalities experienced when considering intragenerational, intergenerational, interspecies, and cosmopolitan justice in a territory or in a particular domain within a territory

	Intragenerational	Intergenerational	Interspecies	Cosmopolitan
Contribution to environmental degradation	How do different social groups contribute to environmental degradation (e.g., air pollution, climate change, biodiversity loss...)?	How do current activities within the territory impact the activities of future generations within their planetary boundaries?	How do human activities within the territory impact the abilities of non-human life to exist and flourish?	How do the activities within the territory contribute to environmental degradation beyond its borders?
Distribution of environmental goods and burdens	How are environmental goods (e.g., green spaces, energy...) and burdens (e.g., air pollution, climate risks...) distributed between different social groups?	How do current activities within the territory impact the ability of future generations to access environmental goods (e.g., clean air, green spaces, quiet spaces...)?		How do the environmental impacts of the activities within the territory are distributed within and beyond its borders?
Impact of environmental policies	How are the impacts of environmental policies of the territory experienced by different social groups?	How do current environmental policies of the territory impact future generations?	How do environmental policies of the territory impact the abilities of non-human life to exist and flourish?	What are the impacts of environmental policies beyond the borders of the territory?
Participation in environmental policy- and decision-making processes	How are different social groups involved/represented and influential in policy- and decision-making processes on environmental issues?	How are the needs of future generations represented and influential in policy- and decision-making processes on environmental issues?	How are the needs of non-humans represented and influential in policy- and decision-making processes on environmental issues?	How are populations beyond the borders of the territory involved/represented in and influential in policy- and decision-making processes on environmental issues?
Recognition of the needs of vulnerable/ vulnerabilized groups	How are the needs of vulnerable/ vulnerabilized groups in the territory considered in the political and social realms?	How are the needs of the most vulnerable/ vulnerabilized groups among future generations considered in the political and social realms?	How are the needs of threatened species and ecosystems considered in environmental policy and plans?	How are the needs of the most vulnerable/ vulnerabilized groups beyond the border of the territory considered in the political and social realms?

While we advocate for a holistic social-ecological policy approach to enable the just transition, we focus in this reflection on environmental policies and their potential impact on particular populations. While not explicitly mentioned, it is essential that other vulnerabilities, related to, e.g., income, education, and race, are address alongside these social-ecological injustices. In other words, while we focus here on distributive, procedural, and recognition dimensions of justice, it is essential that *capabilities justice* is given equal weight in transition policy.

3. Evaluating Social-Ecological Inequalities in Mobility in Brussels-Capital Region

In the table below (Table 2) we propose an example of how to apply the socio-ecological inequalities framework to a specific domain on a city scale, taking the case of mobility in the BCR. This example identifies different inequalities that need to be taken into account to ensure a just transition of the urban mobility system. This is an illustrative example of how one can identify social-ecological inequalities and is not intended to be exhaustive.

Table 2 Assessing social-ecological inequalities in mobility in the BCR

	Intragenerational	Intergenerational	Interspecies	Cosmopolitan
Contribution to environmental degradation	There are relatively more car owners in relatively wealthier municipalities of the BCR, which suggests that wealthier households contribute more to GHG emissions and air pollution associated with car use.	The GHG emissions associated with car use today depletes the carbon budget of future generations.	Transport infrastructure replaces, reduces, and fragments the habitat of other species, leading to an increased mortality and reduced fitness.	The Brussels population, through their mobility habits, contribute more than populations in the global south to climate change.
Distribution of environmental goods and burdens	The most disadvantaged neighbourhoods are the most affected by air pollution associated to car use.	Road infrastructure planning to support the dominant car-use today means that future generations will live in highly concrete environment increasing their exposure to heat waves.		The extraction of raw materials to electrify the car and bicycle fleet outsources environmental damage to the sites of extraction, which tend to be in the Global South.
Impact of environmental policies	The impact of measures to restrict and regulate car use in the city has a more negative effect on car-dependent inhabitants such as people working night shifts.	Car restricting policies could increase housing prices for future generations because they tend to enhance the attractiveness of neighbourhoods.	The air quality benefits due to the introduction of the low emission zone (LEZ) will improve the ability of non-human species to exist and flourish.	Policies to restrict the most polluting vehicles may favour the export of poor-quality used vehicles fleets and associated pollution to regions with lower environmental standards.
Participation in environmental policy- and decision-making processes	Marginalized populations tend to lack representation in key urban development and transport planning forums.	The lack of long-term impact assessment of mobility policies means that future generations may be exposed to unintended consequences of these policies.	The needs of non-humans, as they are represented by environmental organizations, are still underrepresented in decision-making on mobility in the BCR.	There was a lack of participation by interregional commuters in the design of the LEZ in the BCR.
Recognition of the needs of vulnerable/ vulnerabilized groups	The current focus of mobility planning on the needs of commuters tend to neglect the needs of other mobility users.	Current mobility spending (e.g., on the Metro Line 3) depletes future budget for maintaining and improving surface lines that are more essential to vulnerabilized groups (e.g., 70% of the resident population depends on surface lines ²).	Road infrastructure and traffic organization can consider threatened species and ecosystems when being planned (e.g., The OZON project in the Forêt de Soigne, which reconnected ecological hotspots and the habitats of various target species by means of infrastructure (ecoducts, ecotunnels and wildlife fences)).	The protection of inhabitants of countries from which the rare earth elements needed to manufacture electric car batteries are extracted are not considered by policies in favour of the electrification of the car fleet.

4. Conclusions

In this policy brief, we have proposed a tool that could be used by different actors, including public institutions, to evaluate the state of socio-ecological inequalities in the context of just transitions. In the BCR where just transition has become a guiding principle of climate policy, this tool is aimed at

² See Dobruszkes (2008).

supporting the implementation of the main just transition commitments made by the regional government to assess the current state of environmental and social inequalities and identify levers to reduce them.

Based on a multidimensional justice framework, the tool includes a set of guiding questions for assessing the state of multiple social-ecological inequalities in a territory or in a specific domain within a territory. We have illustrated its application by exploring social-ecological inequalities in the mobility domain in the BCR. Although this is only a short example to demonstrate the tool, policymakers are encouraged to expand upon this initial assessment for a thorough evaluation of present and (potential) future social-ecological injustices in the BCR.

More importantly, putting this tool into practice is the first step in developing comprehensive and consistent policy mixes to tackle social-ecological inequalities with a view to ensuring a just transition in the BCR. It further calls for a meaningful and continual participation of all the groups concerned, and especially the vulnerable/vulnerabilized groups. Indeed, both the evaluation of social-ecological inequalities and subsequent development of just transition policy mixes must strive for fair processes integrating the plurality of perspectives, needs, and values.

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